
S.I. Khmelnik

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1493-6630>

About the Designing of Antennas

Theses

1. Antenna design is based on solving Maxwell's equations. The solution to this equations is known and it is on the basis of this solution that antennas are built.

2. However, this solution has a number of shortcomings, in particular,

- a. The energy conservation law is satisfied only on the average,
- b. The solution is inhomogeneous and it is practically necessary to divide it into separate zones (as a rule, near, middle and far), in which the solutions turn out to be completely different,
- c. In the near zone there is no flow of energy with the real value
- d. The magnetic and electrical components are in phase,
- e. In the near zone, the solution is not wave (i.s. the distance is not an argument of the trigonometric function),
- f. The known solution does not satisfy Maxwell's system of equations (a solution that satisfies a single equation of the system can not be considered a solution of the system of equations).

3. These drawbacks actually follow from the fact that there is no solution of Maxwell's equations for a spherical wave in spherical coordinates.

4. The author has found a new solution of Maxwell's equations for a spherical wave in the entire region of wave existence (without partitioning into zones, as is customary in antenna theory) - see Appendix. This solution is free from the indicated drawbacks.

5. The solution obtained of this problem is free from these shortcomings. **In practice, these drawbacks of the known solution mean that they (mathematical solutions) do not strictly describe the real radiation of technical devices.** The main properties of this solution are as follows:

-
- a. The solution is monochromatic.
 - b. The electric and magnetic strengths of the same name (according to coordinates ρ , φ , θ) are phase shifted by a quarter of a period.
 - c. The amplitudes of the transverse wave strengths are proportional to ρ^{-1} .
 - d. There is a longitudinal electromagnetic wave having electric and magnetic components, i.e. there are radial electric and magnetic.
 - e. The energy flux directed along the radius retains its value with increasing radius and does not depend on time, which corresponds to the law of conservation of energy.

6. The obtained solution for an elementary vibrator allows (and, therefore, for their sum)

- 1) at any point of the sphere, find magnetic and electrical tensions (their projections and vectors) - see Fig. 3,
- 2) at any point of the sphere, find the density vector of the radial flux of electromagnetic energy - see Fig. 2,
- 3) calculate the antenna pattern - see Fig. 2,
- 4) take into account in these calculations the distribution density of consumers of electromagnetic wave energy.

7. The resulting solution, being applied in antenna design systems,

- a. should significantly simplify the antenna design process,
- b. will allow you to obtain calculations that are minimally deviating from the results of measuring the characteristics of real antennas built according to the results of design,
- c. due to this, to exclude the laborious and time-consuming process of correcting the results of mathematical design.

8. Therefore, based on the solution found, it is advisable to begin developing a new system for the automated design of antennas.

9. State of affairs:

- Found a rigorous solution to Maxwell's equations,
- Developed experimental programs in the MATLAB system

Appendix

The solution of Maxwell's equations in the **spherical** coordinate system $\{\rho, \theta, \varphi\}$ for vacuum has the following form:

$$E_\varphi = e_\varphi \text{Kh}(\rho, \theta, \alpha, P) \sin(\alpha \varphi + \chi \rho + \omega t), \quad (1)$$

$$E_\theta = e_\theta \text{Kh}(\rho, \theta, \alpha, P) \cos(\alpha \varphi + \chi \rho + \omega t), \quad (2)$$

$$E_\rho = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$H_\varphi = h_\varphi \text{Kh}(\rho, \theta, \alpha, P) \cos(\alpha \varphi + \chi \rho + \omega t), \quad (4)$$

$$H_\theta = h_\theta \text{Kh}(\rho, \theta, \alpha, P) \sin(\alpha \varphi + \chi \rho + \omega t), \quad (5)$$

$$H_\rho = 0, \quad (6)$$

where

$\text{Kh}(\rho, \theta, \alpha)$ is a definite function,

$e_\varphi, e_\theta, h_\varphi, h_\theta, \alpha, \chi, \omega$ are constants, and

$$h_\varphi = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} e_\theta, \quad (7)$$

$$h_\theta = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} e_\varphi, \quad (8)$$

$$\chi = \frac{\omega}{c} \sqrt{\varepsilon \mu}. \quad (9)$$

In this decision

- the density of the energy flux passing through the sphere does not depend on the radius and does not depend on time; this flux has the same magnitude on a spherical surface of any radius at any time; in other words, the energy flux directed along the radius retains its value with increasing radius and does not depend on time, which corresponds to the energy conservation law;
- there is a phase shift between electrical and magnetic tensions, which follows directly from formulas (1, 2, 4, 5);
- spiral propagation of electric and magnetic tensions is observed - see fig. 1,
- swirling of the electromagnetic wave is observed - see fig. 3.

Figures

Figure 1

In fig. 1 shows spirals - geometrical places of points where the density of electrical intensity when multiplied by ρ remains constant. These spirals lie on a cone with an angle θ . Several such cones are shown.

Figure 2

The vectors of the energy flux density at the points of the sphere of a certain radius at a certain value of θ are shown. Charts are shown for multiple radii. Two figures are shown for the same emitter at different radiation powers (this determines the value of α).

Fig. 2. Radiation pattern energy flow (alfa=20)

Fig. 2. Radiation pattern energy flow (alfa=0.2)

Figure 3.

Shown here are vectors of electric tensions on a circle with a given radius of a sphere and a given angle θ . tensions. The start points of these vectors lie on a given circle, and the end points of these vectors lie on a certain curve. These figures illustrate the swirling of an electromagnetic wave. The vectors of strengths $E_t = E_\theta$, $E_f = E_\varphi$, $(\overline{E_t} + \overline{E_f})$ are shown for several values of θ .

